

Mechanically-Interlocked Nanographenes

Nitrogenated

Alberto Riaño^a, Marco Carini,^a Manuel Melle-Franco^b and Aurelio Mateo-Alonso^{a,c*}

^a POLYMAT, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, Avenida de Tolosa 72, E-20018 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain.

^b CICECO - Aveiro Institute of Materials, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal.

^c Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, E-48011 Bilbao, Spain.

Supporting Information

Figure S1. TGA of 1.

Figure S2. TGA of 1@A.

Figure S3. TGA of 1@B.

Figure S4. TGA of 1@C.

Figure S5. Cyclic voltammetry of nanographenes **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** (from top to bottom) in 0.1 M solution of nBu_4NPF_6 in CH_2Cl_2 . Potentials versus Fc/Fc^+ . The values show in the voltammograms correspond to the onset potentials.

Figure S6. Absorption and emission spectra of the reference diamines derivatives (top), thread (mid) and rotaxane (bottom) recorded in chloroform.

Figure S7. Fluorescence spectra of **1@C** in chloroform at different excitation wavelengths (from 290 to 390 nm) illustrating FRET. Rayleigh scattering bands are indicated with asterisks.

	M06-2X-Chloroform-6-31+G(d,p) /M06-2X-6-31G(d,p)			B3LYP-Dichloromethane-6-311+g(2d,p) /M06-2X-6-31g(d,p)		
	abs. / eV	abs. / nm	Osc. Strength	abs. / eV	abs. / nm	Osc. Strength
A	5.22	237	0.2772	4.40	282	0.0485
B	3.41	363	0.4311	3.03	409	0.1829
C	4.29	289	0.4908	3.29	377	0.0198
1	2.76	449	1.0741	2.05	605	0.5858
1@A	2.67	464	0.9037	1.99	623	0.5017
1@B	2.71	457	0.7329	2.00	618	0.4302
1@C	2.74	452	0.5848	2.08	596	0.3477

Table S1. TD-DFT first strong excitations for all systems under study with the B3LYP and M06-2X Hamiltonians. Note that for **1@C**, weak excitations of the predicted conformation also give yield to a higher wavelength broad peak computationally which is experimentally dark.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Commercial chemicals and solvents were used as received. Analytical thin layer chromatography (TLC) was carried out using aluminum sheets (20x20 cm) pre-coated with silica gel RP-18W 60 F254 from Merck. Column chromatography was carried out using Silica gel 60 (40-60 μm) from Scharlab. Compounds **2** and **6** were synthesized as previously described.^{1,2}

NMR spectra in solution were recorded on a Bruker Avance 400 MHz or 500 MHz spectrometer at 298 K using partially deuterated solvents as internal standards.

High Resolution Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization (coupled to a Time-Of-Flight analyzer) Mass Spectrometry experiments were recorded in Biomagune in a Ultraflex III (Bruker Daltonics) MALDI-TOF (frequency-tripled (355 nm) Nd:YAG laser) by Dr. Javier Calvo. Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization (coupled to a Time-Of-Flight analyzer) experiments MALDI-TOF) were recorded on Bruker REFLEX spectrometer in POLYMAT by Dra. Estíbaliz González de San Román Martín.

Absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 spectrometer.

Photoluminescence spectra were recorded on a LS55 Perkin-Elmer Fluorescence spectrometer.

Electrochemical measurements were carried out on a Princeton Applied Research Parstat 2273 in a 3-electrode single compartment cell with Pt disc working electrode ($\varnothing = 0.5$ mm), a platinum wire counter electrode ($\varnothing = 0.5$ mm) and a silver wire pseudoreference electrode. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in dichloromethane solutions and are shown versus Fc/Fc⁺. The HOMO level was estimated from the potential onset of the first oxidation wave ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = - (4.8 + E_{\text{OX}})$) and the LUMO level was estimated from the potential onset of the first reduction wave ($E_{\text{LUMO}} = - (4.8 + E_{\text{RED}})$).

X-ray single crystal diffraction measurements were collected on an Agilent Technologies Super-Nova diffractometer, which was equipped with monochromated Cu $\kappa\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54184$ Å) and Atlas CCD detector. Measurement was carried out at 150.00(10) K with the help of an Oxford Cryostream 700 PLUS temperature device. Data frames were processed (unit cell determination, analytical absorption correction with face indexing, intensity data integration and correction for Lorentz and polarization effects) using the CrysAlis software package. The structure was solved using Olex2 and refined by full-matrix least-squares with SHELXL-97. Final geometrical calculations were carried out with Mercury and PLATON as integrated in WinGX.

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION

Synthesis of compound 3

Under nitrogen atmosphere, a solution of pyrene tetraketone (1.5 g, 4 mmol), tetrabutylammonium bromide (588 mg, 2.8 mmol) and Na₂S₂O₄ (4.178 g, 24 mmol) in DMF (25mL) and H₂O (9mL) were stirred at room temperature during 40 min. After that, bromohexane (5.6 mL, 40 mmol) and K₂CO₃ (5.528 g, 40 mmol) were added and the reaction was heated at 100 °C during 2h. The solution was washed with water, extracted with diethyl ether. The organic phase was washed with water, dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent removed by rotary evaporation. The red-brown crude was purified by chromatographic column (silica gel, hexane) to get a white solid (1.53 g, 53%).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 8.47 (4H, s), 4.33 (8H, *J* = 6.4 Hz, *t*), 1.97 (8H, *J* = 6.4 Hz, *q*), 1.80-1.30 (24H, bs) and 0.94 (12H, *t*, *J* = 6.4 Hz).

¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 148.9, 144.3, 128.3, 119.2, 115.9, 73.9, 35.7, 32.1, 32.0, 30.8, 26.5, 22.9 and 14.2.

MS MALDI (*m/z*): [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₄₈H₇₄O₄: 714.558; found: 714.560.

Figure S8. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of 3

Figure S9. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of 3

Synthesis of compound 4

In a round bottom flask at 0°C, a solution of bromine (134 μ L, 2.63 mmol) in 4 mL of dichloromethane was added dropwise onto a solution of **3** (470 mg, 0.657 mmol) and NaHCO₃ (327 mg, 3.942 mmol) in dichloromethane (40mL). After 5 min, few drops of a solution of Na₂S₂O₃ were added. The reaction was washed with water and extracted with dichloromethane. The organic phase was dried over MgSO₄ and the organic solvent removed under vacuum. The crude was washed with methanol to get a red-orange solid (253 mg, 71%).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 8.50 (2H, d, J = 2.1 Hz), 8.47 (2H, d, J = 2.1 Hz), 4.25 (4H, t, J = 6.4 Hz), 1.90 (4H, q, J = 6.4 Hz), 1.70-1.30 (12H, bs) and 0.93 (6H, t, J = 6.4 Hz).

¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 151.1, 143.7, 136.1, 129.8, 129.7, 127.4, 125.9, 74.1, 31.9, 31.4, 30.6, 26.4, 22.8 and 14.2.

MS MALDI (m/z): [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₃₆H₄₉O₄: 545.3629; found: 545.3622.

Figure S10. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of **4**

Figure S11. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of **4**

Synthesis of tetrabenzotetraazaheptacene (TBTAH) (**1**)

Under nitrogen atmosphere, a solution of **4** (125 mg, 0.229 mmol) and 1,2,4,5-benzenetetramine tetrahydrochloride (**5**) (31 mg, 0.115 mmol) in pyridine (5mL) was stirred at 90 °C during 19h. The reaction was cooled down to room temperature and 7 mL of a solution of HCl 2M were added. The precipitate formed was dissolved in dichloromethane. The organic phase was washed with water, dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The solid was washed with methanol to give 100 mg (76%) of a purple powder.

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 9.70 (4H, d, *J* = 2.0 Hz), 9.53 (1H, s), 8.66 (4H, d, *J* = 2.1 Hz), 4.36 (8H, t, *J* = 6.4 Hz), 1.99 (8H, bs), 1.83-1.12 (24H, bs) and 0.96 (12H, t, *J* = 6.4 Hz).

¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 150.2, 145.9, 143.9, 141.2, 129.1, 128.5, 123.1, 121.8, 121.1, 73.9, 32.0, 30.8, 26.5, 22.9, 14.2 and 1.2.

MS MALDI (m/z): [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₇₈H₉₉N₄O₄: 1155.7663; found: 1155.7677.

Figure S12. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of **1**

Figure S13. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of **1**

Synthesis of 7

HBr in acetic acid (33% wt, 2.1 mL) was added dropwise over a solution of **6** (2.430 mmol, 871 mg) and paraformaldehyde (366 mg) in acetic acid (4 mL). The reaction was heated at 80 °C overnight. After cooling at RT, the precipitate was collected by filtration and washed with water and then with methanol to give the desired the product as a pale yellow solid (1.284 g, 96%).

1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm): 8.13 (2H, s), 4.75 (4H, s), 2.95 (4H, t, $J = 7.1$ Hz), 1.78 (4H, q, $J = 7.5$ Hz), 1.44-1.34 (12H), 0.90 (6H, t, $J = 7.0$ Hz).

^{13}C -NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm): 147.2 136.4, 135.7, 125.6, 114.7, 31.7, 31.0, 29.1, 29.0, 24.4, 22.7, 14.2.

MS MALDI (m/z): $[M]^+$ Calcd for $C_{24}H_{32}Br_2S_2$: 544.029; found: 544.014.

Figure S14. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of 7

Figure S15. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of 7

Synthesis of 8

A solution of **7** (1.658 mmol, 903 mg) and hexamethylenetetramine (4.31 mmol, 604 mg) in chloroform (100 mL) was refluxed during 48h. The mixture was cooled down at room temperature and the precipitate was filtered off and washed with dichloromethane. The solid was suspended in ethanol (145 mL) and concentrated HCl (38 mL) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 48h. The reaction was cooled down and the solid was filtered off and washed with water, ethanol and diethyl ether. The solid was dissolved in chloroform and washed with a saturated solution of NaHCO₃, washed with water, dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent removed under reduced pressure to give 310 mg (45%) of a yellow solid.

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 8.12 (2H, s), 4.04 (4H, s), 2.93 (4H, t, *J* = 7.6 Hz), 1.72 (4H, q, *J* = 7.5 Hz), 1.44-1.34 (12H), 0.89 (6H, t, *J* = 7.3 Hz).

¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 142.8, 137.3, 136.1, 131.5, 114.5, 37.7, 32.0, 31.9, 29.3, 28.9, 22.9 and 14.4.

MS MALDI (*m/z*): [M]⁺ Calcd for C₂₄H₃₆N₂S₂: 416.232; found: 416.128

Figure S16. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of **8**

Figure S17. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of **8**

Clipping reaction (general procedure)

A solution of 20 equivalents of p-xylylenediamine (**10**), 9,10-bis(aminomethyl)anthracene (**11**) or compound **8** and 40 equivalents of triethylamine in dry chloroform (26 mM) and a solution of 20 eq of pyridine-2,6-dicarbonyl dichloride in dry chloroform (26 mM) were simultaneously added to a solution of 1 equivalent of **1** in dry chloroform (4 mM) via motor-driven syringe pump, under nitrogen atmosphere and the reaction was stirring overnight. The crude was filtered through Celite, the solvent was evaporated and the mixture was purified by chromatography column (silica gel, CHCl₃ and then CHCl₃/MeOH 95:5). The unreacted thread was eluted first, followed by the rotaxane that was precipitated from CHCl₃ to MeOH.

Rotaxane 1@A

14 mg, pink powder, 25%.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3 -*d*) δ (ppm): 10.05 (4H, t, $J = 5.3$ Hz), 9.50 (4H, d, $J = 1.8$ Hz), 8.80 (4H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz), 8.73 (4H, d, $J = 1.9$ Hz), 8.63 (2H, s), 8.45 (2H, t, $J = 8.0$ Hz), 5.70 (8H, s), 4.44 (8H, t, $J = 6.4$ Hz), 4.11 (s, 8H), 2.05 (8H, q, $J = 6.4$ Hz), 1.74 (8H, q, $J = 6.4$ Hz), 1.57-1.40 (16H, m), 0.98 (12H, t, $J = 7.0$ Hz).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 164.2, 150.7, 150.2, 146.1, 144.1, 140.2, 139.4, 135.2, 129.5, 128.1, 127.6, 126.4, 126.1, 122.9, 121.8, 121.6, 74.1, 43.8, 35.9, 32.01, 31.7, 30.9, 26.5, 22.9, 14.3.

MS MALDI (m/z): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{108}\text{H}_{125}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_8$: 1689,9600; found: 1688.9515.

Figure S18. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of **1@A**

Figure S19. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of **1@A**

Rotaxane 1@B

22.4 mg, blue powder, 34%.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3-d) δ (ppm): 9.68 (4H, t, $J = 4.3$ Hz), 9.32 (4H, d, $J = 1.7$ Hz), 8.97 (4H, d, $J = 8.1$ Hz), 8.70 (4H, d, $J = 1.9$ Hz), 8.49 (2H, t, $J = 8.1$ Hz), 8.14 (2H, s), 7.07 (8H, m), 5.78 (8H, m), 5.05 (8H, d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 4.47 (8H, t, $J = 6.3$ Hz), 2.09 (8H, q, $J = 6.4$ Hz), 1.79 (8H, q, $J = 6.3$ Hz), 1.56-1.43 (16H, m) 1.00 (12H, t, $J = 6.4$ Hz).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 164.7, 150.4, 150.2, 144.6, 143.9, 138.6, 129.0, 128.9, 128.7, 127.0, 126.9, 124.4, 123.4, 123.2, 121.9, 121.1, 100.1, 74.2, 37.4, 32.0, 31.8, 30.9, 29.8, 26.5, 22.9, 14.3.

MS MALDI (m/z): $[\text{M}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{124}\text{H}_{132}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_8$: 1889.0226; found: 1889.0169.

Figure S20. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of **1@B**.

Figure S21. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of **1@B**.

Rotaxane 1@C

22 mg, 18%.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃-d) δ (ppm): 9.80 (2H, d, *J* = 1.9 Hz), 9.65 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 4H), 9.30 (2H, d, *J* = 2.0 Hz), 8.98 (4H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz), 8.75 (4H, d, *J* = 1.9 Hz), 8.74 (4H, d, *J* = 1.9 Hz), 8.54 (2H, t, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 7.91 (2H, s), 7.10 (4H, s), 5.10 (4H, dd, *J* = 15.2, 9.5 Hz), 4.47 (4H, t, *J* = 6.4 Hz), 4.39 (4H, t, *J* = 6.4 Hz), 3.79 (4H, d, *J* = 15.0 Hz), 2.07 (8H, bs)

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃-d) δ (ppm): 164.4, 150.4, 149.9, 144.9, 144.4, 144.3, 143.7, 143.3, 139.5, 139.3, 137.8, 135.2, 134.2, 129.3, 129.1, 128.9, 128.6, 126.9, 126.5, 122.8, 122.1, 120.8, 120.5, 113.6, 73.9, 73.8, 35.8, 35.7, 35.1, 31.9, 31.5, 30.8, 30.7, 30.1, 29.7, 28.4, 26.9, 26.3, 22.8, 22.2, 14.1, 13.9.

MS MALDI (*m/z*) [M+H]⁺ Calcd for C₁₄₀H₁₇₂N₁₀O₄S₄: 2249.2239; found: 2249.2205

Figure S22. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of $1@C$.

Figure S23. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of $1@C$.

ABSORPTION AND EMISSION PROPERTIES

Compound	$\lambda_{\text{abs max}}$ (nm)	$\lambda_{\text{abs ons}}$ (nm)	ϵ (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	E_{opt} (eV)	$\lambda_{\text{em max}}$ (nm)	Φ_{F}
1	571	628	22417	2.05	629	0.25
1@A	612	662	22007	1.94	643	0.05
1@B	612	662	22521	1.94	649	0.15
1@C	595	646	23209	1.97	636	0.17

Table S2. Absorption and emission spectra were recorded in chloroform at room temperature. Optical band gap estimated from the onset of the absorption spectra. Calculated using Oxacine 170 in EtOH as reference standard.

Figure S24. Absorption spectra of the compounds recorded in chloroform.

Figure S25. Excitation spectra of 1@C recorded in chloroform.

CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRY

Compound	$E^{II'}$ (V)	E^I (V)	E^I (V)	E^{II} (V)	E^{III} (V)	E_{HOMO} (eV)	E_{LUMO} (eV)	E_{gap}
1	-	-	-1.01	-1.22	-1.49	-	-3.87	-
1@A	-	+1.00	-1.14	-1.57	-	-5.71	-3.75	1.96
1@B	+1.10	+0.88	-1.25	-1.80	-	-5.58	-3.65	1.93
1@C	-	+0.80	-1.52*	-2.01*	-	-5.44	-3.62	1.82

Table S3. Reduction potentials *versus* Fc/Fc⁺ in *n*Bu₄NPF₆ in CH₂Cl₂ (0.1 M). All potentials correspond to half-wave potentials but those indicated with stars that correspond to peak potentials. LUMO energies have been estimated from the onset potentials of the first reduction waves according to $E_{LUMO} = -e(4.8 \text{ V} + E_{onset})$. HOMO energies have been estimated from the onset potentials of the first oxidation waves according to $E_{HOMO} = -e(4.8 \text{ V} + E_{onset})$.

X-RAY CRYSTALLOGRAPHY DATA

Identification code	a20190321_ARCF56
Empirical formula	C ₇₈ H ₉₈ N ₄ O ₄
Formula weight	1155.60
Temperature/K	150.00(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	9.6475(4)
b/Å	12.2070(3)
c/Å	15.1821(6)
α/°	78.322(3)
β/°	89.961(3)
γ/°	73.353(3)
Volume/Å ³	1674.41(11)
Z	1
ρ _{calc} g/cm ³	1.146
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.538
F(000)	626.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.281 × 0.203 × 0.068
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	8.71 to 137.992
Index ranges	-10 ≤ h ≤ 11, -14 ≤ k ≤ 13, -18 ≤ l ≤ 16
Reflections collected	11710
Independent reflections	6192 [R _{int} = 0.0210, R _{sigma} = 0.0290]
Data/restraints/parameters	6192/0/396
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.035
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0408, wR ₂ = 0.1061
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0480, wR ₂ = 0.1129
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.25/-0.18

Table S4. Crystal data and refinement of **1**

Identification code	a20200029_ARCD741
Empirical formula	C ₁₃₁ H ₁₃₇ Cl ₁₄ N ₁₀ O ₈
Formula weight	2475.80
Temperature/K	150.01(10)
Crystal system	orthorhombic
Space group	Pbca
a/Å	21.0784(11)
b/Å	32.3068(14)
c/Å	36.4404(11)
α/°	90.0
β/°	90.0
γ/°	90.0
Volume/Å ³	24815(2)
Z	8
ρ _{calc} g/cm ³	1.325
μ/mm ⁻¹	3.333
F(000)	10360.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.776 × 0.106 × 0.062
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	6.972 to 137.998
Index ranges	-25 ≤ h ≤ 23, -39 ≤ k ≤ 39, -41 ≤ l ≤ 44
Reflections collected	202197
Independent reflections	23062 [R _{int} = 0.2410, R _{sigma} = 0.1119]
Data/restraints/parameters	23062/217/1632
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	0.986
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.1014, wR ₂ = 0.2524
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1771, wR ₂ = 0.3101
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.84/-0.89

Table S5. Crystal data and refinement of **1@B**

COMPUTER MODELS

Geometries

There is a crystal structure available for **1@B** but not for **1@A** and **1@C**. We have used a computational methodology to predict, in-silico, a representative structure. For **1@C**, we performed a conformational search based on molecular dynamics simulated annealing to explore the possible minima with the GFN2-xTB Hamiltonian. The GFN-xTB (Geometry, Frequency, Non-covalent, extended Tight-Binding) method allows computing efficiently systems with thousands of atoms.³ The different minima thus found were minimized and ranked by energy at the M06-2X-6-31G(d,p) level. This yields very similar structures and energies, all within chemical accuracy, to the ones obtained from the minimization of **1@A** and **1@B** conformations obtained from XRD analysis which showcases the robustness and the high predictive accuracy of the GFN2-xTB conformer exploration followed by DFT refinement. In addition, the vibrational frequencies of the best DFT minima for each system were computed within the harmonic approximation and were found to be all positive.

Interestingly, while **1@A** and **1@B** show hydrogen bonding to the two N of the sides of the same pyrazine ring. The predicted structure of **1@C** presents hydrogen bonds two different pyrazine rings:

Figure S26. Predicted structure of **1@C**.

Binding energies

Interestingly, the binding energies in solution computed at the M06-2X-Chloroform-6-31G(d,p)/M06-2X-6-31G(d,p) level for **1@A** and **1@B** are similar: 1.5 eV and 1.6 eV respectively, while for **1@C** a larger value, 1.9 eV is obtained. The fact that a similar energy ordering is obtained in gas-phase models, with energies of 2.0 eV, 2.3 eV and 2.8 eV for **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** respectively, indicates that a consistent part of the binding is due to the interaction between **1** and the different macrocycles.

Orbitals

Figure S27. HOMO (bottom) and LUMO (top) for the macrocycles and the thread at the M06-2X-Chloroform-6-31+G(d,p)/M06-2X-6-31G(d,p) level.

B3LYP-Dichloromethane-6-311+G(2d,p)/M06-2X-6-31G(d,p)								
	LUMO+3	LUMO+2	LUMO+1	LUMO	HOMO	HOMO-1	HOMO-2	gap
A	-1.66	-1.71	-1.77	-1.79	-6.66	-6.67	-7.03	4.87
B	-1.76	-1.77	-2.07	-2.19	-5.5	-5.58	-6.71	3.31
C	-1.68	-1.7	-1.78	-1.79	-5.53	-5.54	-6.14	3.74
1	-1.54	-1.84	-1.87	-3.17	-5.63	-5.81	-5.94	2.46
1@A	-1.67	-1.93	-1.99	-3.27	-5.67	-5.85	-5.99	2.4
1@B	-1.89	-1.99	-2.08	-3.21	-5.37	-5.41	-5.64	2.16
1@C	-1.69	-1.86	-1.92	-3.14	-5.24	-5.4	-5.65	2.1

Table S6. Frontier orbitals computed with the B3LYP Hamiltonian with the 6-311+G(2d,p) basis set in chloroform on geometries optimized at the M06-2X-6-31G(d,p). The colour code is: LUMOs, HOMOs and gaps. All values in eV.

	M06-2X-Chloroform-6-31+G(d,p)/M06-2X-6-31G(d,p)		
	EA (LUMO)	IP (HOMO)	gap(EA+IP)
1	-3.08	6.19	3.11
1@A	-3.26	6.21	2.96
1@B	-3.22	5.90	2.69
1@C	-3.13	5.92	2.80

Table S7. Vertical ionization potentials (IP) and electron affinities (EA), gap (EA+IP) at the M06-2X level with the 6-31+G(d,p) basis in chloroform from M06-2X-6-31g(d,p) geometries. **All values in eV.**

References

- (1) Hu, J.; Zhang, D.; Harris, F. W. Ruthenium(III) Chloride Catalyzed Oxidation of Pyrene and 2,7-Disubstituted Pyrenes: An Efficient, One-Step Synthesis of Pyrene-4,5-diones and Pyrene-4,5,9,10-tetraones. *J. Org. Chem.* **2005**, *70*, 707.
- (2) Kashiki, T.; Shinamura, S.; Kohara, M.; Miyazaki, E.; Takimiya, K.; Ikeda, M.; Kuwabara, H. One-pot Synthesis of Benzo[*b*]thiophenes and Benzo[*b*]selenophenes from *o*-Halo-Substituted Ethynylbenzenes: Convenient Approach to Mono-, Bis-, and Tris-Chalcogenophene-Annulated Benzenes. *Org. Lett.* **2009**, *11*, 2473.
- (3) Bannwarth, C.; Ehlert, S.; Grimme, S. GFN2-xTB—An Accurate and Broadly Parametrized Self-Consistent Tight-Binding Quantum Chemical Method with Multipole Electrostatics and Density-Dependent Dispersion Contributions. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2019**, *15*, 1652.